

SYNERGISTIC DELAMINATION TOUGHENING OF COMPOSITES USING NANO- AND MACRO-SCALE REINFORCEMENTS

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ABSTRACT

The use of through-thickness reinforcements such as z-pins is a highly effective method for increasing the delamination resistance of fibre-reinforced polymer composites. This paper presents an experimental investigation showing that dispersing various types of carbon nanofillers within the epoxy matrix of z-pinned laminates can induce a synergistic improvement to the mode I interlaminar fracture toughness properties. Carbon nanofillers that were added into the epoxy matrix include carbon nanotubes (CNTs), carbon nanofibres (CNFs) and graphene nanoplatelets (GNPs). The CNTs promote a higher synergistic toughening effect (~38%) on the mode I delamination resistance than the CNFs. The greater than additive improvement is due to the CNTs or CNFs imparting a dual-scale toughening effect by enhancing the interlaminar fracture toughness and the toughening efficacy of the z-pins. No synergistic toughening effect was observed when adding GNPs in the z-pinned laminates.

1 INTRODUCTION

A long-standing problem with laminated fibre reinforced epoxy composites is their low interlaminar fracture toughness properties leading to susceptibility to delamination cracking. Several approaches have been developed to increase the mode I delamination resistance, including reinforcing the epoxy matrix with nano-scale carbon-based fillers, such as carbon nanotube (CNTs), carbon nanofibres (CNFs) and graphene nanoplatelets (GNPs) [1-3]. More notable approaches at substantially improving interlaminar fracture toughness properties include the insertion of macro-scale through-the-thickness reinforcements (i.e. 3-D stitching or z-pinning) within the composite preform [4-7].

Until very recently, nano-scale and macro-scale reinforcements were used separately to increase the delamination resistance of composite materials. Ravindran et al.[2, 8, 9] and Ladani et al.[10] recently reported that the interlaminar fracture toughness of z-pinned carbon fibre reinforced

composite laminates can be improved even further by adding CNFs within the polymer matrix phase. It was reported that adding a low weight fraction of CNFs (i.e. 1wt%) into the epoxy matrix of a z-pinned laminate promotes a synergistic toughening effect on the steady-state mode I interlaminar toughness (G_{Ic-ss}) that exceeds the expected additive toughening effect when both CNFs and z-pins are used separately [10]. The synergistic toughening effect is induced by the CNFs increasing both the matrix-pin interfacial failure stress and the friction stress during pin pull-out [2, 8, 9]. The reported greater-than additive enhancements are dependent on the CNF and z-pin content [2, 8, 9]. However, it is not known whether other types of carbon-based nanofillers (i.e. CNTs or GNPs) can also promote synergistic toughening in z-pinned laminates.

The present study determines the effect of carbon nanotubes (CNTs) or graphene nanoplatelets (GNPs) on the mode I interlaminar fracture toughness properties of z-pinned carbon fibre reinforced epoxy composite laminates. The efficacy of CNTs and GNPs on the synergistic toughening effect is compared to CNFs. Due to their aspect ratio, CNTs and CNFs are considered one-dimensional (1D) nanofillers whereas GNPs is a two-dimensional (2D) nanofiller. The mechanisms responsible for the greater-than expected additive toughening effects are also determined.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

Four types of carbon-epoxy laminate were investigated: (i) unmodified laminate (i.e. without carbon nanofillers and z-pins), (ii) nanofiller reinforced laminates (i.e. containing CNTs, CNFs or GNPs), (iii) laminate containing z-pins only, and (iv) multi-scale reinforced laminates containing both carbon nanofillers and z-pins. All the laminates were made with 20 plies of 200 gsm plain woven T-300 carbon fabric (AC220127 supplied by Colan Ltd.). The polymer matrix phase was a two-part bisphenol-A based epoxy resin (Resin-105 and Hardener-206 supplied by West System®) [2, 8, 9].

The laminates containing the nanofillers were manufactured by blending either CNTs (Multi-walled carbon nanotubes (~4 μ m length and ~10 nm diameter), 791431 supplied by Sigma-Aldrich®), CNFs (Pyrograf® - III, grade PR-24-XT-HHT (50-200 μ m length and 70-200nm diameter) supplied by Applied Sciences Inc.) or GNPs (XGNP® H-25 (~25 diameter and ~15nm thickness) supplied by XG Sciences) into liquid epoxy resin at a content of 1 wt%. The nanofillers were dispersed in the epoxy resin by hand mixing and then three roll-milling, with further details provided in [11-13]. After the three-roll milling process, hardener was then added to the liquid epoxy resin containing the dispersed nanofillers and then applied to the carbon fabrics using the wet hand lay-up process. The epoxy-impregnated fabrics were stacked into the laminate preforms. Before the resin gelled and cured, z-pins made of a pultruded rod of unidirectional carbon fibre/bismaleimide (supplied by Albany Engineering Composites Pty Ltd.) were inserted in the through-thickness direction of the laminates using a hydraulic press. The z-pins had a diameter of 510 μ m and were inserted into the laminates at a volume content of 2%. The laminates were consolidated and cured using liquid compression moulding at an applied pressure of 350 kPa and temperature of 25°C, as further details of the manufacturing process are described in [2, 8, 9]. All four types of laminates had a final thickness of ~5 mm.

Double cantilever beam (DCB) were manufactured from the different types of laminate. The mode I fracture toughness values were measured using the DCB coupons in accordance with ASTM D5528-13 [14]. A schematic of the DCB specimen is shown in Fig. 1. The DCB samples were tested at a crack opening displacement rate of 1.0 mm/min using 10kN Instron universal testing machine. The crack resistance load, crosshead displacement and crack propagation length (measured via a travelling optical microscope) were recorded to calculate the interlaminar fracture toughness.

Figure 1: Schematic of double cantilever beam specimen also showing the location of the z-pins.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Mode I delamination toughening using nanofillers

The mode I interlaminar fracture toughness values and crack growth resistance curve (i.e. R-curves) for the different types of carbon nano-reinforced laminates are presented in Table 1 and Fig. 2. The mode I fracture toughness of the unmodified laminate and the composites containing carbon nanofillers increased over the first 5-15 mm of crack extension due to the fibre bridging between the plies behind the advancing crack tip and then plateaued to a steady-state value [2].

Composite Type	G_{Ic-i} (kJ/m ²)	G_{Ic-i} Improvement	G_{Ic-ss} (kJ/m ²)	G_{Ic-i} Improvement
<i>Unmodified</i>	0.25 (± 0.03)	-	0.73 (± 0.04)	-
<i>CNTs</i>	0.43 (± 0.04)	72 %	0.92 (± 0.07)	26 %
<i>CNFs</i>	0.54 (± 0.11)	116 %	1.40 (± 0.12)	91 %
<i>GNPs</i>	0.34 (± 0.08)	36 %	1.23 (± 0.12)	68 %
<i>z-pins</i>	0.25 (± 0.10)	0.0 %	5.08 (± 0.25)	595 %
<i>CNTs + z-pins</i>	0.42 (± 0.05)	68 %	6.98 (± 0.25)	856 %
<i>CNFs + z-pins</i>	0.55 (± 0.13)	120 %	6.70 (± 0.20)	817 %
<i>GNPs + z-pins</i>	0.35 (± 0.06)	40 %	5.71 (± 0.36)	682 %

Table 1: Mode I initiation (G_{Ic-i}) and steady-state (G_{Ic-ss}) fracture toughness values of the laminates.

Figure 2: Experimentally measured mode I crack growth resistance curves for the laminates containing unmodified epoxy, CNT, CNF and GNP modified epoxy.

All the nanofillers were effective at increasing the mode I delamination resistance of the laminate. The magnitude of the toughening was dependent on the type of nanofiller, with CNFs more effective at improving the mode I initiation (G_{Ic-i}) and steady-state (G_{Ic-ss}) interlaminar fracture toughness (see Table 1). As shown in Fig. 3, the nanofillers increased the delamination resistance via multiple intrinsic toughening mechanisms which include interfacial debonding, microcracking, crack bifurcation and plastic void growth within the process zone immediately ahead of the main crack tip [2, 15]. These intrinsic mechanisms promoted to enhancements observed on the mode I initiation fracture toughness. Extrinsic toughening that were observed include the short-scale bridging and pull-out of the nanofiller just behind the crack front [16].

Figure 3: (a) Schematic of the mode I toughening mechanisms along the crack front of the epoxy interlayer, located between the plies. Scanning electron microscope (SEM) images of the fracture surface of DCB laminate samples containing (b) unmodified epoxy, (c) CNT, (d) CNF or (e) GNP modified epoxy matrix.

3.2 Mode I delamination toughening using z-pins

Z-pins, when used on their own in the laminate, promoted an even greater improvement to the G_{Ic-ss} values than when the nanofillers when used separately as shown in Table 1 and Fig. 4a. This greater toughening efficacy was due to the large-scale bridging of the z-pins along the mode I delamination cracks as shown in Figs. 4b and 4c. The large-scale extrinsic toughening processes occur within the laminate at long crack propagation lengths (i.e. ~25-30 mm) [8, 17]. However, no improvements were observed on the mode G_{Ic-ss} values.

Figure 4: (a) Mode I crack growth resistance curve z-pins. (b-c) Computer tomography (CT) scan images of the z-pin bridging process .

3.3 Mode I delamination toughening using carbon nanofillers and z-pins

Combining the carbon nanofillers (CNTs, CNFs or GNPs) with the z-pins to create the multi-scale reinforced laminates magnified the improvements to the mode I fracture toughness properties shown in Table 1 and Fig. 5. The increase to the toughness (i.e. $\Delta G_{nano-fillers+z-pins}$) far exceeded the improvement expected from an additive toughening effect from the corresponding carbon nanofillers ($\Delta G_{nano-fillers}$) and z-pins (ΔG_{z-pins}) when used separately (see Fig. 6). This synergistic toughening effect ($\Delta G_{synergy}$) can be quantified using the expression [8]:

$$\Delta G_{synergy} = \Delta G_{(CNF+z-pins)} - (\Delta G_{nano-fillers} + \Delta G_{z-pins}) \quad (1)$$

The percentage synergy for these laminates can be calculated using [8]:

$$Synergy (\%) = \frac{\Delta G_{synergy}}{\Delta G_{(nano-fillers)} + \Delta G_{(z-pins)}} \times 100\% \quad (2)$$

Figure 5: Mode I crack growth resistance curves (i.e. R-curves) of the multi-scale reinforced laminates containing (a) z-pin + CNT, (b) z-pin + CNF and (c) z-pin + GNP.

Figure 6: Percentage synergistic improvements to the mode I steady-state interlaminar fracture toughness of the multi-scale reinforced laminates concerning the effect of nanofiller type.

As shown in Table 1 and Fig. 6, CNTs and CNFs were the most effective in promoting a synergistic toughening effect for mode I delamination crack growth, respectively. Previous work into the effect of combining CNFs with z-pins has shown that the synergistic toughening is induced by the additional traction energy CNFs impart towards the z-pin bridging response under mode I conditions. The CNFs increase the failure stress of the matrix-pin interface and frictional resistance of the z-pins to pull-out which increases the crack bridging traction energy which in turn increases the fracture toughness [10]. The CNTs also induced the synergistic toughening effect from the same mechanisms as the CNFs. This was evident by the increased roughness of the epoxy composite interface upon which the z-pins were pulled-off from, as shown in Fig. 7. The pull-out of the CNTs and CNFs contributed to increase surface roughness, hence increased the frictional resistance of the z-pins during the bridging process (see Figs. 7b and 7c) [2]. However, the GNPs were ineffective at synergistically increasing the mode I fracture toughness properties of the z-pinned laminates. As shown in Fig. 7d, fractographic examination revealed that there no GNPs were present along the surface z-pin/epoxy interface. This is due to the two-dimensional shape and size of the GNPs, which restricted their capacity to increase the pull-out traction energy of the z-pins.

Figure 7: Schematic and SEM images comparing the mode I pull-out surface along the z-pin/composite interface containing (a) unmodified epoxy, (b) CNTs, (c) CNFs and (d) GNPs in the epoxy matrix.

4 CONCLUSIONS

Combining one-dimensional carbon nanofillers (CNTs, CNFs) with z-pins leads to synergistic improvements to the mode I interlaminar fracture toughness of carbon fibre reinforced composites. When used concurrently, the toughening effect from nanofillers and z-pins exceeds the expected additive toughening when the CNTs or CNFs and z-pins are used separately. The synergistic toughening is induced by the 1D nanofillers increasing the toughening efficacy of the z-pins. Two-dimensional nanofillers such as GNPs investigated within the present study do not induce a synergistic toughening effect in z-pinned laminates.

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